

The Implications of IATF Protocols to the Employees Job Performance on Selected Jollibee Branches in Dasmariñas City

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Abstract: The creation of the IATF Protocols was made to aid the employees and employers with rules, regulations, and safety protocols that were imposed once the business is operating during this pandemic. One of the main reasons why the IATF Protocols were implemented is to become a guideline for the employees that will still be working during the pandemic. Jollibee Corporation is one of the largest fast-food chains in the Philippines, and it is also one of the largest firms that have health workers who work 24/7 onsite. To learn more about the employees' understanding of the implemented IATF protocols, the researchers conducted a study to determine the effects of the IATF protocols on the job performance of an employee. The results show that the demographic profile of the majority of the respondents under the age of 25 and those who graduated from senior high school and above understand the protocols and follow them thoroughly. Imposing mandatory training and health programs such as mandatory vaccinations, basic health practices in schools and workplaces, and management awareness are some of the recommended advocacies that the researchers want to establish using the study.

Keywords: Employees, IATF, Workplace, Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

Life before the pandemic started was rich in hustles and bustles of life that were illustrated everywhere. Children playing in the streets, teenagers hanging out with their group of friends, and employees managing, preparing, and working everyday are all examples of what you might observe. People who work at fast-food restaurants are preoccupied dealing with and managing customers at their branch that is sometimes open 24/7. We often see the prosperity of the Food and Service Industry in the Philippines before the pandemic and how Filipinos portray their love for food and also bond with their loved ones. Fast-food chains are known for their fast service and quality food, which is why Jollibee is known for being one of the most successful, and the best places to dine that serve the best Filipino dishes like sweet spaghetti with hotdogs, Palabok, and others. According to an article published in GMANetwork.com (2022), The Jollibee Group has been recognized by the Asian Wall Street Journal as the most admired company in the Philippines for ten consecutive years. In addition, Forbes named Jollibee as one of the World's Best Employers, the World's Top Female-Friendly Companies, and one of Asia's Fab 50 Companies. The Jollibee Group became the first Philippine-based firm to obtain the Exceptional Workplace Award from Gallup in 2020. This achievement made the Jollibee Group the first recipient of the award.

The global pandemic affected a percentage of the world's population, which caused the implementation of several safety protocols for every establishment. According to Mina et al. (2020), the government of the Philippines has imposed a strict lockdown that will last for several months in Luzon due to the increasing number of COVID-19 cases. Employees have

been cautious about getting the virus from their workplace, prompting some of them to choose to work from home setup instead. Businesses must re-open, and many people must return to work while adjusting to significant changes in their daily routines. Government officials, employees, businesses, and organizations created health and safety rules, guidelines, and measures to improve the progress in reducing the number of cases and providing a safe workplace, as well as protect the well-being of employees and their families. To manage the COVID-19 virus, the government has sponsored activities such as plans for prevention, awareness, and pandemic, which forced businesses to take extreme precautions as the country attempts to manage the virus that affected the employees.

President Duterte, Rodrigo R. convened the Inter-Agency Task Force on the Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) in the first half of March 2020. The Executive Branch consists of various departments mentioned in this executive directive. Dr. Francisco Duque III led the Department of Health and oversaw managing the IATF-EID. Furthermore, IATF-EID is inter-sectoral cooperation formed to build preparation and guarantee effective government response in the Philippines to evaluate, assess, manage and prevent potential pandemic cases. A system must be developed to identify and aid Filipinos who show signs of EID, as well as to limit and/or reduce the admission of suspected or confirmed EID cases into the country, and to prevent and/or minimize the regional spread of EID in the Philippines. Officials have established non-certified procedures aimed at reducing COVID-19 cases, preventing infection, and supporting people who were infected. According to Beyza, E. (2021), although precautions have been implemented in the workplace to limit the spread of COVID-19, alternative alternatives have not been made available to all employees.

Furthermore, Beyza claims that the fact that the country has yet to establish a viable treatment approach or vaccine for the pandemic has caused worry and anxiety among many employees by creating ambiguity about the process's course. Moreover, De Vero (2021) said it is important to underline that the country is still a long way from reaching the goal of controlling the said virus. Several considerations have been raised concerning this subject. Some people have complained that some Filipinos do not follow the necessary protocols, while the government lacks a plan, and people have protested for a pandemic solution. When the first case of COVID-19 was discovered, some claimed that the Philippine government did nothing.

When it comes to poor performance, researchers have frequently examined the influence of these various variables; nevertheless, they have not always investigated the effects of the other aspects impacting the workers' performance, including their personal lives and obligations. In addition to their professional challenges and concerns, the service crew may be dealing with family or personal issues that interfere with their performance at work. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) (2021), workplace transmission of COVID-19 continues to be a challenge in the Philippines, and dedicated efforts are needed to break the chains of transmission to save lives and livelihoods.

“The Philippines has been profoundly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic resulting in loss of lives and livelihoods. As we support the response to the pandemic, we also need to support economic revival by ensuring the safety of workplaces. The health and safety of entire workforce are of utmost importance,” said Dr. Rabindra Abeyasinghe, WHO Representative to the Philippines. To protect those at risk, it is imperative that the local health systems re-double their efforts to implement effective infection, prevention, and control strategies that include workplaces.

Worker protection measures against coronavirus exposure and infection are based on the level of exposure. The risk varies depending on the type of job, the amount of human interaction, and the risk of contamination in the workplace. To assess and mitigate these factors, employers should conduct a thorough risk assessment and implement robust infection, prevention, and control strategies, including contact tracing, to keep workplaces open and operational. Building capacity and strengthening information-sharing practices with respective local health offices is crucial to these efforts and will allow for a more coordinated and effective response. WHO will continue to support DOH and response partners to make workplaces healthier and safer by strengthening prevention and response systems to prevent, detect and respond to COVID-19 cases and establish information sharing across LGU boundaries and settings to enhance response efforts.

According to Cruz (2020), the Joint Memorandum Circular No. 20-04-A Series of 2020 outlines the Workplace Safety & Health Regulations to safeguard every worker from accident, disease, or death by providing safe and healthy working conditions. Furthermore, Cruz stated that the Joint Memorandum Circular will provide everything for workers at every plant and that personnel is strongly encouraged to follow IATF and DOH safety rules when performing their jobs in the workplace. Due to the scenario and work environment present, various institutions or enterprises follow different protocols, but the objective is to protect the well-being and safety of the employees. On June 29, 2020, Resolution No. 50 of the IATF

was recommended to continue to open up the economy while assessing techniques to increase public belief in returning to work and Increasing the effectiveness of mitigation strategies in the stringent enforcement of the public health standards.

Memorandum Circular No. 92 discusses the responsibilities of the management and their workers, which states that if an employee fails to comply with or follow the rules because of poor performance, such as excessive absences, they can be terminated at any time; however, there are some instances in which they can still be given a second chance by the company for which they are working. It also explains how to make an accurate assessment of a situation. Hence, employees may form their own opinions about how the firm treats them based on the circumstance and the attention shown to them. The Memorandum will serve as the legal basis going forward. Jollibee Food Corporation is one of the most well-known fast-food companies in the world, with stores all over the world. Furthermore, because it focuses on employees' performance and how the company or organization deals with its employees on a day-to-day basis, this will aid the researchers in gathering reliable and legal information for the research study.

The researchers conducted the study to determine the effects of implemented IATF Protocols on the job performance of Jollibee

employees into their workplace. Jollibee has always been a favorite dining and gathering place for the Filipino people and has designed a tagline, "Bida ang saya!" to emphasize their commitment to service for their consumers. This phrase represents the company's core objective and commitment. Also, they have employees who put committed to their jobs and willingness to deliver services despite being exposed to COVID-19 risks and possibilities. The IATF strictly inspected food and service industry employees to ensure that the employees will strictly follow the protocols. As Filipinos, the researchers value their countrymen and their contributions to the country's development and the research was made to advocate and empower fast-food employees regarding their struggles amidst the pandemic and the effects of IATF Protocols instituted on them.

Conceptual Framework

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, issues of the workers' safety, health, and well-being have been known to the public. Every day, the COVID-19 sickness causes an infection that can infect multiple healthcare workers in a day (Rothwell, 2020). Because the potential of infection is always there, vital employees must live in constant fear of being exposed and in a state of uncertainty. The COVID-19 pandemic has gained a negative influence on the whole well-being of the critical employees that had contact with members of the general public even when they are ordered to stay at home due to the disease. The contact between people resulted in more stress by the ambiguity surrounding the infection status of others.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

In Figure 1, the Input-Process-Output Model was used for the theoretical framework. According to Sorensen et al. (2016), the conceptual model can aid in the formulation of research hypotheses and priorities for the investigation of the factors that can influence the security, wellness, and health of workers. The chart shows the Input-Process-Output Method the researchers used to identify the covered topics and the strategies used to investigate the problem, utilize solutions, and create programs. The first column depicts the demographic profile of the employees of the three selected branches of Jollibee in Dasmariñas. It is used to collect and review the data for the second column, which will explain the methodology and the instruments used in the study. Furthermore, the researchers will utilize the Four Performance Metrics to evaluate, analyze, and support the employees' performance at work. IATF protocols, on the other hand, will allow us to determine the guidelines for the employees' workplaces and businesses to follow. Next is to create and evaluate treatments and

programs that are relevant to the employees and employers. Finally, the researchers are expecting the following outcomes and plans for the last column, which include: proposed and enhanced training that will be conducted by the Jollibee Food Corporation for the employees to develop their professional capabilities; their job involvement, and commitment; and the highest levels of performance are all priorities.

The Statement of the Problem

This study focuses on scrutinizing the effects of IATF Protocols to the Employees' Job Performance in Dasmariñas City. The goals are to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants in terms of?

1.1 Age

1.2 Educational Background

1.3 Shift Work

2. How do the respondents perceive the effect of IATF Protocols to the employees' job performance in terms of;

2.1 Quality of Work

2.2 Employees Efficiency

2.3 Individual Goals

3. Is there a significant difference on the respondent's perception of the effect of IATF Protocols to the employees' job performance when grouped according to demographic profile?

4. What program can be proposed and enhanced to improve the employees' job performance this time of pandemic?

The Statement of Hypothesis

There is no significant difference on the responses addressing participants' assessments of the effects of the pandemic on employees' job performance.

The Review of Related Studies

According to De Vero, M.K., and colleagues (2021), many preventative measures were implemented due to the COVID-19 global pandemic. De Vero et al. (2021) said that a nationwide action plan to combat COVID-19 was created as part of the Interagency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases' preventative measures (IATF) and the National Task Force (NTF) to keep the virus from spreading throughout the country. Immediately following this, the government implemented the Prevent, Detect, Isolate, Treat, and Reintegrate (PDITR) plan to "cope with the new normal," as they put it. This method has been implemented to prevent the spread of the virus and ensure the health and safety of community members. Additionally, this method urges constituents to continue to adhere to the minimum health requirements, which include frequent hand washing, the use of a face mask and a face shield, and the practice of social distance from others. To ensure that vaccinations were distributed efficiently, the government established a regional priority system for the vaccine purchase and distribution program.

An intuitionistic fuzzy DEMATEL analysis of the Philippine government lockdown relaxation protocols in response to the COVID-19 pandemic (2020)

According to Ocampo, L. et al., the Philippine government formed the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) responsible for monitoring and making recommendations on all government actions linked to the COVID-19 pandemic (2020). The GCQ status is a lowering of the ECQ status level that includes the re-establishment of economic activity measures. Executive Order No. 112 specifies the transition rules from ECQ to GCQ after a two-month shutdown. To reduce viral transmission, the guidelines prescribe a set of actions with clear commonalities that are intended to maintain social distance, good sanitation, and limited individual movement in order to slow viral transmission while gradually resuming certain vital socio-economic activities.

The government's Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) was created to keep the coronavirus infection from spreading. The federal government stated that the new occupational safety rules would be enforced by May 7, 2020, in places under

enhanced and broad community quarantine. According to Presidential Spokesperson Harry Roque, new work arrangements for employees, such as working from home arrangement and shift rotations, will be adopted. The length of meetings that require physical attendance must be kept to a minimum, with only a limited number of employees permitted to participate. This conforms with the rule of physical distance between parties, and the following rules must be followed by employee standards: 1. Consistent application of face masks 2. Workstations must be physically separated from one another. 3. Barriers must be used to separate workstations. 4. Workstations should be placed away from aisles and walkways. 5. Elevators can only carry a limited number of passengers. And finally, 6. The use of stairwells should be promoted (Nakpil, 2020).

A Phenomenological Investigation of Service Crews' Lived Experiences During the COVID-19 Pandemic (2021)

According to Escoto et. al (2021) Studies have shown that eased quarantine allowed more locations to resume, even though travel was prohibited due to the pandemic. The social system limits everyone's potential. Caution loss from the dining area while shutting the service crew and client. On the other hand, some are unable to use public utilities because of the measures imposed; they are still worried about contaminating their family or loved ones. To guard against possible cases of the virus, they established alternative means of food collection, delivery, and collection.

Pandemic employees are to return to work and managers will guarantee that their staff's well-being and safety are being monitored. Despite their challenges, employees were grateful that they still had careers, unlike those who had lost their jobs due to the pandemic. Due to extra sanitation practices and costs, compared to regular food delivery teams have found it impossible to provide services. More time is needed to maintain service-crew survival health protocols. Job crews had a hard time regardless of the pandemic. All activity is confined to the parameters.

WHO supports efforts to enhance workplace safety systems to curb the spread of COVID-19 in the Philippines (2021). On April 30, 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) Country Office in the Philippines, in collaboration with the Department of Health (DOH) Center for Health Development Metro Manila and the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), held a session on the COVID-19 Response of the Workplace for safety officers of local government units (LGUs).

The level of risk determines the measures taken to protect workers from COVID-19 exposure and infection. The level of risk varies according to the type of work, the level of interaction with people, and the contamination of the work environment. To assess and mitigate these factors, employers should conduct a thorough risk assessment and implement robust infection prevention and control strategies, including contact tracing, to keep workplaces open and operational. Building capacity and strengthening information-sharing practices with respective local health offices is crucial to these efforts and will allow for a more coordinated and effective response.

WHO (2021) According to the report, commissioned safety officers from various local government units (LGUs) across the country attended the workplace session. It also supplemented the Department of Labor's 40-hour mandatory Basic Occupational Safety and Health Training Course for Occupational Safety and Health Services. WHO will continue to provide support to DOH and response partners to make workplaces healthier and safer by strengthening prevention and response systems to prevent, detect, and respond to COVID-19 cases and establishing information sharing across LGU boundaries and settings to enhance response efforts.

The researchers aim to understand how IATF protocols affect the work performance of the service crews or workers of the three selected branches of the Jollibee Food Corporation in the City of Dasmarinas in Cavite and to understand the effects of different IATF protocols implemented on the employee performance in a particular company in different areas. The limited movement and communication of each employee can cause poor performance an employee, which can result in low evaluation by the company they work for. Additionally, the researchers expect to learn about the effectiveness of every service crew while IATF Protocols are implemented during this pandemic; the causes and risk of poor performance of the service crew; the quality of work and efficiency of the employees; and finally, the relevance and negative impact of the IATF Protocols on the job performance of the employees. Moreover, after identifying the problems and acquiring the objectives of the research, the next step is to engage in assisting, programs, knowledge, and awareness to the beneficiaries of the study.

The 3 Performance Metrics

Four measures will be used to evaluate the employees' performance. Evaluating and assessing employee performance consistently and accurately is crucial not just to individual achievement but also to the success of the business as a whole. The employees' performance will be evaluated on an individual basis based on these four measures, which will give the employee a better picture of how they can assess themselves in business.

Quality of Work indicates that quality generates a high quantity and standard not only in products but also in the work of employees.

Employee efficiency is defined as employees being organized and well-mannered when executing or finishing a task that will help the company grow and enhance its position in the industry. Additionally, this will save time and effort required for each employee, improving job quality.

Individual Goals are the set of goals the employees' plan for themselves. The employer must interact with and create goals for the employees to set characteristics and standards in their job. This measure will assist the employer in recognizing the various perspectives, needs, and desires of every employee. It is critical to be noticed and given equal attention.

Performance measurements are important throughout the whole employment lifecycle. In the recruiting process, applicants might discover that performance is not just controlled but is encouraged and supported to guarantee that everyone on the team succeeds. Employees are provided with the chance for continual improvement during their career, with performance indicators serving as the primary tool for identifying areas of opportunity. Personal success and performance management are aligned with corporate objectives because of this transformation in the employee experience. Adopted from Namely (2021)

The quarantine protocol amendment, according to CNN Philippines, includes the following procedures: the active case finding in all areas, the tracing of suspected, probable, and confirmed cases' close contacts within 24 hours of case detection, Cases and close contacts were immediately quarantined and tested, and those who tested negative on rapid antigen testing were subjected to RT-PCR testing.

Local government units (LGUs) and regional epidemiological monitoring units are also responsible for identifying areas with case increases or clustering and submitting samples for sequencing as soon as possible, in addition to ensuring that workplaces and establishments conduct daily health and exposure screening. Reporting identified cases and close ties to the LGU, coordinating investigation and response, and considering workplace incentives to encourage reporting and adherence to isolation measures are all important steps.

In addition to the COVID-related activities listed below, employers must make all relevant workplace safety and health programs available to their employees at no cost.

Proper use of a mask, according to Brooks JT, Beezhold DH, and Noti JD, is a simple barrier that can help keep your respiratory droplets from spreading to others. According to studies, wearing a mask over the nose and mouth reduces the spray of droplets. Wearing a mask protects those around you if you are infected but do not show symptoms.

Face shields, according to Elizabeth Hanes, BSN, RN, provide a great level of protection to the wearer. They cover the entire face—mouth, nose, and eyes—and they prevent a large percentage of virus particles from reaching the user. Face shields are arguably the most effective at preventing coughing and sneezing.

"Physical separation," according to the WHO, helps limit the spread of COVID-19, which means keeping at least 1 m between us and avoiding spending time in crowded places or groups. Safeguard yourself and others. The transmission line must be severed.

Regular cleaning and disinfection can also reduce the risk of infection. Cleaning with soap or detergent minimizes the number of bacteria in areas by removing pollutants while lowering the risk of germs from surfaces.

Posting signs or visual cues and reminders: Placing signages or visual aids and reminders: Employees are required to post signage or visual signals as well as reminders to practice washing their hands properly and other hygiene practices. The employees are expected to sanitize the surfaces of their workstations at the start of the shift, at regular intervals throughout the shift, and at the end of it. Finally, employees are discouraged from sharing personal items to avoid potential transmission.

Contact and Duration: Employees are required to limit physical contact inside the premises, especially when doing large gatherings. Also, they are encouraged to limit staff interaction. Their workplace must have signs, physical barriers, and other measures to guarantee compliance.

Upon entering the building premises/workplaces, all employees must fill out the Health Declaration Form, or a soft copy. Individuals experiencing symptoms will be directed to appropriate entry points into the health system, such as a primary care facility or a health consultation.

The IATF said that the importance of this policy is that it provides adequate direction and appropriate data to all workers and encourages them to ensure that Filipino laborers throughout the nation are aware of how to safeguard themselves, their peers, and their family members from the risks of COVID-19. It can also help them to feel less anxious in their place of employment. The goal is to meet the needs of customers efficiently and effectively by establishing a procedure excellence system that allows for constant improvement, related constraints, and variability reduction, among other objectives.

II. METHODOLOGY

For this study, the researchers will utilize Quantitative Research using the Descriptive Method, which will be applied in determining the number of participants and gathering and analyzing data. Furthermore, researchers will use a survey questionnaire to obtain information for this study, which will help them understand the consequences of various IATF Protocols on employees of selected Jollibee branches in Dasmarinas City.

Participants of the Study

The employees of the Central Mall, DBB-1, and SM Market Mall branches in Dasmarinas, Cavite, are the study's specific respondents.

The study would use the Sampling Size Formula to determine the required number of samples to be included in the study and based on the sampling size computation.

The researchers' criteria for selecting study participants are that respondents must be employees of the three Selected Jollibee Branch. The researchers would be able to collect the necessary data for the study by using them as specific respondents.

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The Research Design

To examine the perceptions of workers in Dasmarinas Cavite, the study employs Quantitative Research and Purposive Design in data collection procedures. Quantitative research aims to raise awareness and comprehension of the IATF protocols and its method of learning about a specific group of people known as a sample population. A process-oriented quality management system that allows for continuous supply chain improvement, defect prevention, variation, and waste reduction.

Research Locale

The purpose of the study is to enumerate and explain the various IATF protocols and guidelines affecting the job performance of Jollibee employees of Central Mall, DBB-1, and SM Market Mall in Dasmarinas City Cavite Branches. Establishments or Businesses are strictly advised to follow these IATF protocols to ensure the safety of personnel while working. Also, the mentioned food establishment may have a basis or checklist regarding the area or problem that needs to be improved to boost the job performance of the employees, this would be beneficial to the mentioned food establishment's management as they can gain awareness of the things they should focus on regarding the job performance of the employees and the IATF Protocols, and lastly, it is also beneficial to the employees for it helps them understand or know the factors that affect their job performance considering the guidelines implemented.

The location to be used in conducting the research is through the online platforms available. Due to the Covid Pandemic, Researchers have decided to use Google Forms as it is one of the most accessible tools in the new normal. Research would be conducted in the 2nd semester of School Year 2020-2021.

The Sampling Size formula would be used by researchers to determine the number of samples required for the study. The formula for calculating sample size is given below. Researchers calculated a total of 30 respondents using the method provided by the participants. As a result, because the researchers were unable to determine the number of individuals they would utilize for their population size, they settled on the maximum population size of 100 people.

The sample size calculator from Raosoft Inc. will assist the researchers in obtaining their results. It was then calculated using the above formula with a confidence interval of 2.58, a sampling error of 1%, and a target population of 30%.

The Researchers would use the online platform to gather the necessary data required to finish the study. Due to the Covid Pandemic, the Researchers have decided to use Google Forms as it is one of the most accessible tools in the new normal and to distribute their questionnaires to the respondents safely.

The quota Sampling Method is defined as a sampling method in which researchers are to create a sample involving individuals that makes a representation of the population. The researchers would establish criteria to be followed in choosing the respondents to be included in the study.

The sampling technique to be used by the Researchers is the Quota Sampling method as the Researchers' study "*The Implications of "IATF Protocols to the Employees Job Performance on Selected Jollibee Branches in Dasmariñas City"*" would conduct and gather its data from a specific group of people, samples are selected based on whether they fit the criteria for the target respondent of the Researchers. In the case of the Researchers, the only source of valuable data would only come from those who work inside of Jollibee thus making them the requirements of the Researchers in looking for the target respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers gathered information through a survey questionnaire that used google forms. It is composed of questions that will provide research basic information about the respondents' demographic profiles.

Furthermore, the researchers employed Likert scale survey questions, it included the degree to which respondents agree or disagree with the given statement.

The data was obtained through a survey to ensure that each respondent can answer the question with no biased opinion. The questionnaire was sent to the participants, and the researchers will discuss the survey, because the name is optional, and the survey will be completed anonymously. Lastly, the data gathered will be used solely for this research.

Data Analysis

The survey data was statistically analyzed using methods such as T-test/Analysis variance, frequency percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation.

The data was sorted in a frequency distribution table according to their category. Using relative frequency percentage, the researchers can determine the most frequently occurring demographic information used in visualizing different factors that may affect the respondents' answers.

Furthermore, the second part of the questionnaires which utilize a Likert scale type of survey will be analyzed upon tallying data and computing the weighted mean. Each question's information will be computed individually, and each mean can be used in computing the standard deviation. Standard deviation can illustrate the dispersion of data from the mean and can also somehow define the consistency of the data gathered.

In addition, to analyze the level of significance of this information the researcher will use a T-test for the singular population. It can provide a conclusion for the decision-making of whether to accept and reject the null hypothesis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the data gathered is presented, investigated, and interpreted. To fully demonstrate and present the accuracy of the data based on the objectives stated in the study, which are to analyze the level of comprehension and awareness of the respondents based on the indicators that the study inputs, to provide suggestions, and to reinforce students' awareness of the implications of the IATF Protocols to the job performance of the Jollibee employees, and to fully show and present the accuracy of the data based on the objectives stated in the study.

Statement of the Problem #1

1. Demographic Profile of the respondents.

1.1 Age

Frequencies of 1.1 Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 25 and below	18	60.0	60.0	60.0
26 – 30	3	10.0	10.0	70.0
31 – 35	8	26.7	26.7	96.7
36 and above	1	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.1 reveals the demographic profile of the respondents according to their age. The figure shows that most of the respondents belong to the category of 25 and below years old having 18 out of 30 or sixty-point zero percent (60.0%). Furthermore, the second group that consists of most of the respondents is 31 – 35 years old which consists of 8 out of 30- or twenty-six-point seven percent (26.7 %). Moreover, the third sector is composed of 26 – 30 years old out of 30 respondents or ten-point zero (10.0%). On the other hand, the category that got the least number of respondents is 36 and above out of 30 respondents or three-point three (3.3%).

The figure indicates that people 25 and below years old, not that old, and not those young are more likely to have an understanding and awareness when it comes to IATF Protocols.

The findings are far from the study of Amegayibor, G.K. also the age range that they use is similar enough to the study, the most frequent age group in their study is in the category of 25 – 35 years old or forty-five percent (45%) of the population. In conclusion, younger people have the most comprehension and knowledge of IATF Protocols and the implications they have for their performance on the job.

1.2 Educational Background

Frequencies of 1.2 Educational Background

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid College	17	56.7	56.7	56.7
High School	4	13.3	13.3	70.0
Senior High School	8	26.7	26.7	96.7
Undergraduate	1	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents according to their Educational Background. The college students have a total percentage of 56.7%, while the Highschool students have a total of 13.3%, Senior High School students have 26.7% total, and lastly Undergraduate has only a total of 3.3%. With a total percentage of 100%.

In conclusion, most of the employees are college students that has 56.7% total percentage and the lowest in the ranking is the undergraduate that only got 3.3%. Majority of the employees in this study that are working while IATF Protocol is implemented are college students.

1.3 Shift Work

Frequencies 1.3 Shift of Work

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1:00 PM - 9:00 PM	8	26.7	26.7	26.7
11:00 AM - 7:00 PM	3	10.0	10.0	36.7
3:00 PM - 11:00 PM	7	23.3	23.3	60.0
9:00 AM - 5:00 PM	12	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of the respondents according to their Shift of Work. It shows that the 9:00 AM to 5:00 PM shift has the highest percentage of 40%, followed by the 1:00 PM to 9:00 PM shift which has a total of 26.7%, next is the 3:00 PM to 11:00 PM shift which has a total of 23.3% and lastly is the 11:00 AM to 7:00 PM shift that only got a 10% in total. It shows that the number of employees working in the daytime is higher than the employees working at night time.

In conclusion, this table shows that the majority of the employees are working in daytime with the total of 40% and with lowest in the rank which is 10% in total.

Statement of the Problem #2

Factors that perceives the effect of IATF Protocols to the employees' job performance

In terms of the following:

1. Quality of Work	mean	Std.dev	Verbal interpretation	rank
1.1 I am confident in dealing with customers and moving around our workplace since our management provides complimentary safety hygiene kits (masks, alcohol, and face shields)	3.47	.507	Agree	1
1.2 I find difficulties in hearing/understanding customers' concerns as face masks and face shields are used all the time	3.30	.702	Agree	6
1.3 physical distancing creates difficulties in communication with colleagues and customers	3.40	.498	Agree	4
1.4 Maintaining physical distance reduced actions and work space, making it time-consuming for employees to complete various jobs and obligations.	3.27	.640	Agree	7
1.5 Disinfection of Employees are strictly implemented to avoid spreading of the virus that can cause a massive sickness around the workplace that will extremely affect their performance.	3.37	.718	Agree	5
1.6. "Wet floor" signages are placed if needed so that employees can avoid accidents and be unable to perform well at work.	3.40	.563	Agree	3
1. 7. I can perform my job properly and at my very best because the workplace is at its best state.	3.43	.568	Agree	2
Over all mean	3.3762	.40836	Agree	

Table 1.1 shows the quality of work, revealing that statement 1.1, "I am confident in dealing with customers and moving around our workplace since our management provides complimentary safety hygiene kits (masks, alcohol, and face shields)" has the highest mean, which is three-point forty-seven percent (3.47%) with the verbal interpretation of "agree." While statement 1. 7. "I can perform my job properly and at my very best because the workplace is in its best state." has the second-highest mean, which is three-point forty-three percent (3.43%). I agree with the verbal interpretation of "agree." The statements 1.6. "Wet floor "signals are placed if needed so that employees can avoid accidents and be unable to perform well at work. " 1.3 "Physical distancing creates difficulties in communication with colleagues and customers." have the same meaning, which is three points forty percent (3.40%) with the verbal interpretation of "Agree." On the other hand, statement 1.5, "Disinfection of employees is strictly implemented to avoid the spread of the virus that can cause a massive sickness around the workplace that will extremely affect their performance." is the fifth in the rank that has a mean of three-point thirty-seven percent (3.37%) with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." Moreover, statement 1.2 "I find difficulties in hearing/understanding customers' concerns as face masks and face shields are used all the time" has a mean of three-point thirty percent (3.30%) with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." Lastly, statement 1.4 "Maintaining physical distance reduces actions and workspace, making it time-consuming for employees to complete various jobs and obligations." has the lowest mean with three points twenty-seven percent (3.27%) with a verbal interpretation of "Agree."

The results show that the employees agreed that IATF Protocols are affecting their performance at work. Nevertheless, they are willing to comply, adapt, learn, and understand the IATF Protocol that is essential for the new normal.

Companies need a high quality of work-life (QWL) to keep getting and keeping employees. It's what an employer does to improve the lives of their workers. QWL is a department-wide, all-inclusive program that aims to improve employee satisfaction, strengthen learning at work, and help employees deal with change and transitions better. Almost all workers

are unhappy with the quality of their work, no matter how high up they are or how important they are. Many managers work to reduce dissatisfaction at all levels of the organization, including their own. But this is a hard problem to solve because it's hard to pick out and name all of the things that affect the quality of work life. The workplace is a good place to work because it has both obvious and hidden benefits. You can see or feel these good things. QWL is based on the idea that for a business or institution to be a good employer, it must know that its employees have lives outside of work (and, for that matter, during work as well). This makes employees more trustworthy and loyal, which is good for everyone and makes the world a better place. (Saraji G.N. et.al 2021)

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2.2 Employees Efficiency

2. Employee's Efficiency	mean	Std.dev	Verbal interpretation	rank
2.1. I provide clear and detailed service while wearing face shields and masks, assuring our customers' safety and comfort.	3.43	.504	agree	4
2.2 I find the use of face mask, and face shield affects my communication with customers	3.47	.507	agree	3
2.3. The facilities of our store are adjusted in terms of space so that the employees can perform well while following the physical distance.	3.40	.498	agree	6
2.4. Signages are properly placed to avoid obstacle and difficulty while employees perform their tasks. And also to inform people about COVID-19.	3.43	.504	agree	4
2.5. All restroom are packed with necessities to avoid bacterial contact that can affect the employees' stability in performing their tasks.	3.53	.507	strongly agree	2
2. 6. Employees are strictly told to follow rules in sanitizing tools, kitchenware and facilities to avoid sickness that can make them less productive at work.	3.60	.498	strongly agree	1
2. 7. I have difficulties in communication with customers because of minimized interaction and contact to surface.	3.27	.640	agree	7
Over all mean	3.4476	.35736	agree	

In terms of Employees Efficiency, the highest percentage has three-point sixty (3.60%) which implies Strongly Agree in the verbal interpretation, wherein Employees are strictly told to follow rules in sanitizing tools, kitchenware, and facilities to avoid sickness that can make them less productive at work. Whereas the difficulties in communication with customers minimized interactions and contact to surface got the lowest rank having the percentage of three-point twenty-seven (3.27%) which indicated as Agree in verbal interpretation.

The results of the respondents imply strongly agree that the employees are strict in following the rules inside the workplace. This shows that most employees are afraid to get in contact with the virus that might affect their performance at work or can slow them down in terms of productivity. It also shows that health is the top priority of every employee to perform at their best while in the workplace.

According to WorkSafe Victoria (2020), Employers should provide adequate training for employees to minimize risks to health and safety, such as training on the correct use of personal protective equipment if it is required, good hygiene practices, and updated cleaning procedures. This means that employees and employers/companies should be updated in terms of Covid-19 guidelines to ensure the safety of all the staff in the workplace.

2.3 Individual Goals

3. Individual Goals	mean	Std.dev	Verbal interpretation	rank
3.1 I keep my performance consistent with the aid of our management, which monitors my situation and the challenges I face at work while following the IATF's protocols.	3.43	.504	agree	2
3.2 I am secured in meeting the demands, and needs of customers while following IATF Protocols because our management talks about the pandemic's challenges and changes to us, employees.	3.53	.507	strongly agree	1
3.3 I am experiencing distress and pressure in accomplishing and delivering my work accurately and on time because of the IATF Protocols implemented during this time of pandemic.	3.40	.498	agree	5
3.4. The management holds seminars about new rules on a regular basis so that employees don't cause confusion and instability at work, which could slow down their productivity.	3.40	.498	agree	3
3.5. The IATF protocols helped us to better the facility which allows us to have much confidence to work safely, effectively and efficiently.	3.37	.669	agree	6
3. 6. Our management is unaware of the situation and the difficulties we face such as mental health issues that may cause poor service while adhering to the company's and IATF protocol	3.30	.596	agree	7
3. 7. I face more stressors than ever before including working remotely and worrying about health due to the virus, since we interact with different customers.	3.40	.563	agree	3
Overall mean	3.4048	.36582	agree	

In terms of Individual Goals, the highest percentage has a three-point fifty-three (3.53%) which implies Strongly Agree in verbal interpretation, wherein the Employees are secured in meeting the demands and needs of customers while following IATF Protocols because the management talks about the pandemic's challenges and changes to them, employees. Whereas the management is unaware of the situation and difficulties that the employees face such as mental health issues that may cause poor service while adhering to the company's and IATF protocol only got a less percent which is equivalent to three-point thirty (3.30) in verbal interpretation.

The results of the respondents imply strongly agree that the management or the company is adjusting based on the employee's needs while working under the IATF Protocols, with this being said employees can function at their 100% at work without having the fear of being contacted by the virus because the company is securing their safety.

According to International Labour Organization (2020) By having a comprehensive emergency preparedness plan in the workplace crafted to address health crises and pandemics, workplaces may be better prepared to develop a quick, coordinated, and effective response, while adapting the measures to the specific emergency that the enterprise is facing (ILO, 2020i). Continuous monitoring of OSH conditions and appropriate risk assessment will be required to ensure that control measures related to the risk of contagion are adapted to the specific evolving processes, conditions of work, and characteristics of the workforce during the critical period of contagion and afterward, so that reoccurrences may be prevented.

Statement of the Problem #3

Is there a significant difference on the respondent's perception of the effect of IATF Protocols to the employees' job performance when grouped according to demographic profile?

3.1 Group by Age

	Mean	Std. Deviation	f- comp	p-value	decision	Interpretation
QW 25 and below	2.6032	.12546				There is a significant difference
26 – 30	2.9048	.16496				
31 – 35	2.8750	.31887	4.656	.010	Reject Ho	
36 and above	2.5714	.				
Total	2.7048	.23409				

EE	25 and below	3.1667	.28676					
	26 – 30	3.6190	.21822					
	31 – 35	3.3214	.23844	3.333	.035	Reject Ho	There is a significant difference	
	36 and above	2.8571	.					
	Total	3.2429	.30048					
IG	25 and below	2.6667	.18334					There is no significant difference
	26 – 30	2.6667	.21822					
	31 – 35	2.8036	.34941	2.355	.095	Failed to Reject Ho		
	36 and above	2.1429	.					
	Total	2.6857	.25829					

The table reveals those aged 26–30 years old have the highest mean in terms of the factors, which are quality of work, employee efficiency, and individual goals. While those aged 36 and up have the lowest mean deviation.

which indicates that much younger ages have more knowledge about the quality of work, employee efficiency, and individual goals. since they are more exposed compared to those ages 36 and above.

To further analyze the data, the result of the study reveals the employees’ awareness and level of understanding of IATF Protocols when grouped by age.

This means that the respondents have the same level of understanding and awareness of the quality of work, employee efficiency, and individual goals when grouped by age.

On the other hand, the table also shows above shows that regarding employees’ awareness and level of understanding of IATF Protocols has both significant and no significant difference when grouped by age by Quality of Work, Employee Efficiency, and Individual Goals since the F values for Quality of Work and Employee Efficiency are 4.656 and 3.333 and have a p-value lower than the level of significance of .010 and .035 or (10% and 35%). Individual Goals have an F value of 2.355 and a p-value greater than the level of significance of .095, indicating that no significant difference exists.

This indicates that the null hypothesis of both having no significant difference is rejected and accepted, while the alternative hypotheses are both accepted and rejected.

This means that when respondents are grouped by age, they have the same level of understanding and awareness of the quality of work, employee efficiency, and individual goals. As a result, ages 26–30 and 31–35 above play a significant role in the level of awareness of IATF Protocols. ages 36 and above, and 25 and below, do not play a significant role in the level of awareness of IATF Protocols.

3.2 Group by Educational Background

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid College	17	56.7	56.7	56.7
High School	4	13.3	13.3	70.0
Senior High School	8	26.7	26.7	96.7
Undergraduate	1	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

The table shows that respondents in their college have a higher mean than those in the other year, who have a lower mean deviation. As a result of their experiences and exposure to the subject, respondents in college are more knowledgeable about the implications of IATF Protocols.

3.3 Group by Shift of Work

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1:00 PM - 9:00 PM	8	26.7	26.7	26.7
11:00 AM - 7:00 PM	3	10.0	10.0	36.7
3:00 PM - 11:00 PM	7	23.3	23.3	60.0
9:00 AM - 5:00 PM	12	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

This demonstrates that the 9:00 AM to 5:00 PM shift has the highest percentage of 40%, followed by the 1:00 PM to 9:00 PM shift with a total of 26.7 percent, the 3:00 PM to 11:00 PM shift with a total of 23.3 percent, and the 11:00 AM to 7:00 PM shift with a total of 10%. This demonstrates that the number of employees working during the day is greater than the number of employees working at night.

IV. CONCLUSION

In terms of their demographic profile, most of the respondents grouped according to Age belong to the category of 25 and below years old that have the most comprehension and knowledge of IATF Protocols and the implications they have. The data also revealed that Senior High School students have the highest awareness of IATF protocols when grouped according to Educational Background. When it comes to Shift Work, most of the respondents work from 9:00 AM to 5:00 PM.

For the factors that perceive the effect of IATF Protocols on the employees' job performance in terms of Quality of Work, the majority of the respondents agree that to improve employee satisfaction, companies should have a high quality of work-life to strengthen learning at work, and help employees deal with change and transitions better. When it comes to Employee Efficiency, results revealed that the respondents strongly agree that the employees are strict in following the rules inside the workplace. In terms of Individual Goals, most of the respondents strongly agree that the management or the company is adjusting based on the employee's needs while working under the IATF Protocols.

As for the significant difference in the respondent's perception of the effect of IATF Protocols on the employees' job performance when grouped according to their demographic profile, for Age, the results indicated that there is a significant difference when it comes to Quality of Work, and Employee's Efficiency. Individual Goals, on the other hand, have no significant difference. The null hypothesis of both has and no significant difference is both rejected and accepted, while the alternative hypothesis is both accepted and rejected. For Civil Status, the findings revealed that employing single personnel makes a difference in terms of quality performance because they do not have as much responsibility at home and can dedicate their time to their job more. For Educational Background, the data showed that Senior High School students are more knowledgeable about the implications of the IATF protocols. For the Shift of Work, the employees working from 9:00 AM to 5:00 PM are greater in number than employees working the night.

Lastly, the training program/plan to improve the employees' job performance during this pandemic is to implement General Health Guidelines for employees to minimize health risks for the customers and to observe health and safety in the food industry such as Mandatory COVID-19 Vaccination, Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) in the Food-Processing Area, Proper and Mandatory Wearing of Uniforms, etc. and Management Health and Safety Practices such as Efficient Workplace Design, "Health Comes First" Policy, Safe Food Sourcing, etc.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter discusses the proposed Training Program/Plan for the Health, and Safety of the Employees. Since the pandemic has a negative impact on the Food and Service Industry, these practices will aid in a better workplace environment, resulting in the welfare and well-being of every employee and customer.

TRAINING PROGRAM/PLAN: EMPLOYEES HEALTH AND SAFETY PRACTICES

General health guidelines for employees to minimize health risks for the customers and to observe health and safety in the food industry.

- 1. Mandatory COVID-19 Vaccination:** Employees should be vaccinated as this will benefit both the employer and employee.
- 2. Practice Physical Distancing, and Minimize Non-Essential Physical Contact:** Arrange places, and things according to its purpose, impose hazards signages, establish lanes and Do Six Feet Away distance
- 3. Hygiene Standard Practices for Employees:** Proper hand hygiene; Application alcohol-based hand sanitizers on a frequent basis; Developing a good respiratory hygiene (cover mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing; dispose of tissues and wash hands); Cleaning and sanitizing work surfaces and handling surfaces such as door handles on a frequent basis; Keeping a safe distance from somebody showing symptoms of respiratory illness (coughing and sneezing)
- 4. Sanitize, and Disinfect: Utilize washing of hands, Implement professionalism, and safety standard in appearance:** Hair net, Hair ties, Hand Gloves, Mask, and Face Shield. Administer disinfecting before, during, and after going to work (Time-to-time if possible)

5. **Proper and Mandatory Wearing of Uniforms:** Implement wearing uniforms as this will protect workers, improve security, prevent product cross-contamination, maintains a professional image

6. **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) in the Food-Processing Area:** PPE should be used regularly in high-risk areas of food facilities that produce ready-to-eat and cooked foods to minimize the risk of cross contamination and unwanted food spoilage

7. **Health and Safety Practices for Transporting and Delivering of Food Ingredients and Food Products:**

- Drivers and other delivery personnel should not enter the establishment during delivery since they may have been infected with COVID-19 or have had contact with someone who has.

- Drivers and other employees should practice good hygiene and physical distancing.

- Drivers must also be aware of the requirement to keep all containers clean and disinfected on a daily basis: foods must be secured from contamination; and must be kept away from other items that could cause contamination.

8. **Limited Number of Employees Within the Area and Proper Assignment of Tasks:** To have a systematic flow of operations; To lessen the unwanted contact and cross-contamination

9. **Maintain a Clean Work Environment:** Regular sanitation and disinfection of the facility.

10. **Practice Proper Food Preparation and Cooking of Food:** Practice general rule for raw meat (frozen food should only be thawed within two hours, never refreeze, etc.); Cooking and storing should be at the right temperature; Raw food must be cooked at a suitably high temperature and stored at an appropriate cool temperature; Cooking food should not be left unattended.

MANAGEMENT HEALTH AND SAFETY PRACTICES

Practices to implement by the management to maintain a safe and healthy workplace as this will positively improve the work environment and operations.

1. **Identify Hazards:** Analyze incident, injury, illness, and relatively close details within the workplace; Survey employees; Analyze findings from enforcement inspections, insurance surveys, or consultations; Follow OSHA regulations; Inspect the workplace

2. **Control Hazards:** Prioritize the hazards discovered; Make plan in correcting and minimizing the occurrence of hazards; Correct the hazards; Evaluate the changes

3. **Train employees:** Train personnel about the hazards they may be exposed to at work and how to protect themselves; Provide full training for general safety, OSHA standards training requirements, and retraining

4. **Efficient Workplace Design:** Ergonomically designed workplace

5. **Continuously Improve System and Policies:** Up-to-date systems and policies to ensure employee health and safety; Developing policies to minimize future risks

6. **Association, and Workers Welfare:** Promote union, compassion, and safe environment among employees. Apply Management between workers: Arrange monthly meetings, programs, and mental health-related talks.

7. **"Health Comes First" Policy:** Employees showing symptoms of COVID-19 are not allowed to enter the establishment without getting COVID-19 testing; Employer should offer COVID-19 testing to employees at no cost; Employees not feeling well are not obligated to come to work

8. **Safe Food Sourcing:** Ingredients should be purchased from legitimate supplier to provide high-quality and secure products.

REFERENCES

[1] Tugade, R, R. (2020). State of Exception.

[2] Mina, J.C. et. al (2020). The Safety and Security Measures of the Selected Universities in Nueva Ecija, Philippines: Its Combat to COVID-19 Pandemic.

[3] GMANetwork.com (2021) Jollibee Group recognized for Outstanding Performance with 2021 ASEAN Business Award for Food and Beverage Sector.

- [4] IATF, S (2020). Omnibus Guidelines on Community Quarantine with Amendments.
- [5] Ocampo, L. et. al (2020) Modeling the lockdown relaxation protocols of the Philippine government in response to the COVID-19 pandemic: An intuitionistic fuzzy DEMATEL analysis.
- [6] De Vero, M.K. et. al (2021) Prevention and planning as important factors in ensuring public health in the Philippines during the COVID-19 pandemic. Volume 43, Issue 2, Pages e358–e359
- [7] Nakpil, D. (2020) Gov't issues new guidelines at workplace for enhanced, general community quarantine.
- [8] Beyza, E. (2021). Impact of Covid-19 Fear on Employee Performance. Journal of Current Research on Social Sciences. Vol.10, SP-845, EP-852.
- [9] Cruz, J. (2020) Joint Memorandum Circular No. 20-04-A DTI AND DOLE Supplemental Guidelines on Workplace Prevention and Control of COVID-19.
- [10] DOLE (2020). Workplace rules set to cut spread of COVID-19.
- [11] Kabagani, K, D. (2020). Containing Covid 19, Mitigating Impacts.
- [12] Escoto, M.R., et. al (2021). A Phenomenological Inquiry into the Lived Experiences of Service Crews Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic, Vol-7 Issue-1 2021., IJARIE-ISSN(O)-2395-4396, pp. 1004-1016.
- [13] Namely (2021) The 4 Metrics to Gauge Employee Performance.
- [14] CNN, PH (2021) IATF approves changes in quarantine protocols.
- [15] WHO (2021) WHO supports efforts to enhance workplace safety systems to curb the spread of COVID-19 in the Philippines?.
- [16] Brooks JT, et al. (2021) Maximizing Fit for Cloth and Medical Procedure Masks to Improve Performance and Reduce SARS-CoV-2 Transmission and Exposure.
- [17] Amegayibor, G.K. (2021) The effect of demographic factors on employees' performance: A case of an ownermanager manufacturing firm. ISSN 2774-8561, Vol 1, No 2, 2021, 127-143
- [18] Saraji G.N. et.al (2021) Study of Quality of Work Life (QWL). Vol. 35, No. 4, 2006, pp.8-14
- [19] Worksafe Victoria. (2020). Managing Coronavirus (Covid-19) risks: Hospitality Industry.
- [20] PRB. (2018), A Demographic Profile of U.S Workers Around the Clock.
- [21] International Labour Organization. (2020), In the face of a pandemic: Ensuring Safety and Health at Work.